

Сам святий в творі є фігурою сакральною. Він з'являється епізодично, лише тоді, коли юні герої повісті потребують фізичної або моральної допомоги. Читач бачить святого Луку тільки через сприйняття цих розгублених підлітків. Причому кожен/кожна з них знаходять в постаті чудесного лікаря щось своє, глибинно-інтимне. Поступово з цих розрізнених, мозаїчних спостережень складається цілісний образ особистості непересічної, титана духу, справжнього подвижника й молитовника, який зцілює не тільки тіла людські, а й душі (що для письменниці є головним).

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PECULIARITIES OF THE VOCATIVE AS A COMPONENT OF THE CONFESSIONAL STYLE OF UKRAINIAN LANGUAGE

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Since the revival of Ukrainian sovereignty, religious and church life has taken the optimal forms and new qualitative certainty. The national church, which has long been in social and ideological isolation, has regained its status as a spiritual institution. The functioning of Ukrainian language in the church and religious

sphere is also being restored: the confessional style is actively developing and become the subject of linguists' attention in recent years.

The linguistic studies devoted to various aspects of confessional vocabulary analysis have appeared in recent years. The functioning of sacred terminology is investigated in the collective monograph "Ukrainian Terminology". The problems of thematic groups separation of confessional vocabulary, semantics, lexicography, spelling, etc. are investigated into the works of N. Babych, S. Bibla, N. Poddubna, etc.

The genre-style differentiation of confessional style remains out of the linguists' attention. It combines texts of the same type in terms of linguistic expression. Within this context, it should be mentioned about the several substyles' separation with peculiarities within the confessional style: prayers, sermons, liturgies, catechetics, etc.

As a result of linguistic studies, we have found that vocatives addressed to listeners are a necessary structural component of public speaking, including sermons. First of all, it performs an etiquette function, facilitates contact between the speakers and the listeners. However, the role of vocatives is not limited by this function. Studying the style of the Gospel Teaching, U.B. Dobosevych noted that vocatives are the most effective means of focusing and maintaining attention in the sermon, the indicator that determines the degree of the saying words' importance [1, p. 8].

The researcher of the Gospel Teacher G. Chuba noted the stylistic expressiveness of the vocatives in the traditional sermon: they are a significant means of influencing the listener and the sermon's concretization. In the texts of the Teaching Gospels, she distinguishes the vocatives with lexeme "brother" (used mainly in the form of plural or assembly), by which Ukrainian preachers tried to create an atmosphere of equality, respect, brotherhood and commitment [2, p. 452; 3, p. 146].

The specificity of the sermon as a type of religious genre is conditioned vocatives to Divine. For the most part, such vocatives are at the end of all the sermon or introductory chapter of the sermon. The vocatives to God, Jesus Christ, are indicated by the enhanced expression achieved by various means: the use of the am-

plifying particle, the possessive pronouns, the amplification of the vocatives expressed in direct nomination and paraphrases.

The lexical component of almost every vocative phrase in these sermons is the word “Orthodox” or “Christian”. As mentioned before, such ideological refinement, according to the religious polemics, was a constant element of vocatives, noted by various genres. However, in sermons addressed to warriors, the semantics of the “Orthodox” / “Christian” definition is changed and becomes in strong opposition to the unorthodox according to the opposition line “us-them”. The emphasis on the ideologue “Orthodox” is achieved by its repetition and affirms the unappealable truth of the Orthodox faith and enhances the conviction in the righteous war against non-Christians, expresses a high positive public appreciation for the warriors who defend the Orthodox motherland.

The vocative is also an important mean of the moral and didactic purpose of preaching. The Gospel texts are the most important source of instructive stories. But by referring to the Bible, the preacher not only quote and interpret it: he evaluates the events, reflects on the actions of biblical characters by imaginary dialogue with them. The vocatives create the effect of the biblical character presence among the listeners, bring the past events to contemporaries, make them find analogies in their own lives.

In addition to biblical plots, sermon texts included narrative elements from legends, parables, fables, educational cases that served to confirm or to prove teaching, religious, or moral explanation.

Therefore, in each sermon, there are vocatives to God and Jesus Christ, which can be considered as one of the defining stylistic features of the sermon as a religious genre. The selection of vocatives is conditioned by the preaching instruction: depending on its content, the vocatives serve to support the pathos, mourning tonality. The rhetorical vocatives have a big stylistic potential in the linguistic context of the sermon. In addition to the semantics of the keyword, stylistic possibilities of vocatives express epithets, intensifying participles, possessive pronouns in combination with expressive means of syntax – amplification and repetition. These peculiarities of folk-speaking style also provided a high artistic level of baroque sermons.

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